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Date of Release: February 3, 2026

Disclaimer and Statement of Purpose

Purpose of the document: The following List of Summaries is a secondary, descriptive factual record of events and administrative decisions informing a professional and scientific dispute regarding research integrity. This document is intended as a factual foundation for the accompanying document titled *Allegations of a Hostile Research Environment at the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG)*, and is provided for the use of relevant oversight authorities, funding agencies, and the scientific community.

While certain communications referenced herein were marked as “confidential” by the issuing bodies, this summary does not reproduce the documents in their original form. Instead, it documents the factual actions and the underlying rationale provided by organizations exercising public or quasi-public functions. As a primary party to these proceedings, the author maintains a protected right to preserve and describe the factual record of their own professional history and the procedural handling of their research integrity reports. While various bodies may have issued unilateral requests for “confidentiality,” the author maintains that such requests cannot legally suppress the disclosure of the substantive reasoning behind decisions made by publicly funded oversight bodies, especially when such decisions concern matters of scientific accuracy and potential maladministration.

In accordance with European and Austrian legal principles, “confidentiality” applies to the protection of personal privacy and trade secrets, but may not extend to a blanket prohibition on describing the logical pillars of decisions made by oversight bodies with public or quasi-public functions. In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and to prevent claims of Creditgefährdung (§ 1330 ABGB), the names of private individuals and non-public figures have been replaced with functional titles (e.g., “PI,” “University Ombudsman,” “Agency Representative”). This document focuses on administrative logic and procedural actions rather than personal identities.

This disclosure is made in the interest of scientific transparency and the protection of public research funds. The author asserts a legitimate interest in documenting the procedural handling of research integrity allegations. Under Article 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), the author exercises the right to discuss and analyze the logical basis of institutional decisions that directly affect their professional standing and the validity of scientific records. These entries are summative descriptions of correspondence and do not constitute a literal reproduction of protected works. This approach respects the distinction between “expression” (copyrighted form) and “facts/decisions” (publicly relevant information). All entities mentioned are presumed to have acted within their perceived mandates.

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[1] Project Proposals

Types: PDF and DOCX documents.

There are 4 proposal drafts:

1) A pre-proposal submitted to the University of Music and Performing Arts (KUG) in November 2019 and accepted on 12.12.2019.

In this pre-proposal, the postdoc researcher asks for a 2-month postdoc fellowship to develop a proposal for a research project to be submitted to the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for a Lise Meitner fellowship, which is dedicated to promoting young researchers and their innovative ideas.

2) An initial proposal to be submitted for a Lise Meitner fellowship.

In this proposal, the postdoc researcher is foreseen to act in the quality of PI of the project. The project aims to study and expand the notion of cadence in music, with cadence being approached through an inquiry “based on the concept of entropy” (p. 8) and its tendency to move from states of order to states of disorder, which forms the core hypothesis.

3) A proposal to be redirected to the Stand-alone Project program (version “final 2”).

In this proposal, the aim of the project remains the same as (2). The mentor is indicated to become PI of the project. The postdoc researcher is reported as the first author of the proposal. The proposal indicates that, during the last five months of research activities, the postdoc researcher would write a monograph, possibly serving as a habilitation.

4) A proposal to be submitted for the Stand-alone Project grant (version “final 3”).

The content of the proposal remains substantially unchanged. The PI is reported as the first author of the proposal, and the postdoc researcher is reported as co-author.

The date of submission of the final proposal is: 4.6.2020.

The date of beginning of research activities is: 1.3.2021.

[2] Proposal of the PI to Change the Project's Destination, from a Lise Meitner to a Stand-alone Project

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 7.5.2020

The email proposes to transform the postdoc project into a Stand-alone Project, mentioning that there is a Ph.D. student that is researching on a topic that is very close to the project's goals. The e-mail includes a draft of the Ph.D. proposal of the student for consultation.

[3] Changes in Content and Unnotified Change in Authorship Order of the Project Proposal

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 1.6.2020

The email contains two attachments, both with filenames starting with “Danieli et al.” The first file (PDF, version “final2”) contains the project proposal with comments from an external adviser. In this version, the postdoc researcher is listed as the first author.

The second file (DOCX, version “final3”) contains highlighted changes to the text. In this version, the PI is listed as the first author; however, unlike the text changes, this change in authorship order is not highlighted. Notably, the filename remains “Danieli et al.” despite the change in the internal document.

In the email body, the PI mentions the external adviser’s comments in the PDF and informs the researcher that he made text changes in the DOCX, and those are marked in yellow. The PI asks the researcher to review these and update the proposal, marking all further changes. No mention is made of the modification to the authorship order.

[4] Rejection of the Project's Approved Core Hypothesis

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 13.5.2021

The PI thanks the postdoc researcher for his letter approaching critical issues in project development and proposes to discuss it in an in-person meeting and suggests postponing further project work until these questions are clarified.

The PI thanks the postdoc researcher for his draft about his thoughts on entropy. The PI characterized the integration of natural science methodologies into musicology as “counter-intuitive” and “confusing.” The PI categorized this approach as an outdated methodological framework from the 1950s–60s that lacked psychological reference.

The PI rejected the researcher's proposal to consider natural predispositions in musical listening. He asserted that such biological or natural-science approaches were no longer viable from his perspective and that the historical use of terms like entropy had been predominantly metaphorical, suggesting that an approach to entropy in a natural sense is problematic in a seriously discussed scholarly context due to developments in music perception.

[5] Communication of Postdoc Research Position at Another University

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 3.2.2022

In this email, the PI forwards to the postdoc researcher an advertisement published by McGill University about their open-position for a postdoc research candidate, asking whether the postdoc researcher was interested in the opportunity.

[6] Formal Statement of Concerns: Abrogation of Leadership Agreement, Methodological Inadequacy, and Technical Flaws in Data Analysis

Type: E-mail

From: Postdoc Researcher

To: PI

Date: 16.4.2022

In this letter, the postdoc researcher makes a review of dynamics related to project leadership. The postdoc researcher states that after writing a project proposal for a Lise Meitner program (FWF), the PI suggested a change in program (FWF, Stand-alone Project) to support a Ph.D. student of his and receive more funding for additional operations, suggesting that the postdoc researcher would be leading the development of the project.¹ The researcher states that he experienced a functional abrogation of this agreement—identifying it as a factual state where the agreement was set aside in practice. The postdoc researcher states that the PI expressed satisfaction for the progress in work activities during the first months of work, until a sudden change in collaborative framework made the postdoc researcher feel “isolated and unheard.”

The postdoc researcher underlines that his research approach (the hypothesis that sonic transitions between pitched and noisy sounds may provoke a perception of closure) was in line with the original proposal, and that the original proposal submitted to the FWF placed strong emphasis on the interrelation between entropic processes and cadential effects, reporting it as a reason for including a specific external adviser.

The researcher reports a sudden shift in the workplace dynamic, feeling that his professional contributions were abruptly devalued following the project’s commencement. The researcher reports that the concept of entropy was not informing the platform designed by the PI for collecting data. The researcher states that he reported concerns about both the research methodology imposed by the PI and his approach to data analysis. The researcher reports that he criticized the research methodology multiple times, and that his previous input on data analysis was ignored. The researcher argues that the current “subjective” approach (relying on the researchers’ own perceptions as a baseline) creates a circular logic that undermines the scientific rigor of the study. The postdoc researcher reports a quote from memory dated 6.4.2022, claiming that the PI entered the office and expressed surprise that the pilot results deviated from his own model, noting the potential impact on the perceived value of the methodology. The postdoc researcher notes that he had consistently communicated this critique for months.

The researcher concludes by proposing a solution which includes his ability to conduct his own research on cadences, noise, and entropy two days per week. The researcher suggests that, if this solution was not possible, he will resign in November.

¹ Original text: “*In May 2021, after writing a project proposal for a 2-years postdoc through the Lise Meitner Program (FWF), you proposed to extend the project to support a PhD student of yours, [name of the student], and receive more funding for additional operations, suggesting I would be leading the development of the project.*”

[7] Response of the PI to the Formal Statement of Concerns of the Postdoc Researcher

Type: E-mail
From: PI
To: Postdoc Researcher
Date: 19.4.2022

Regarding the mentioned understanding on project leadership, the PI acknowledged its existence but asserted a unilateral change in project management. The PI justified this shift by characterizing his own prior involvement as having been more “passively” conducted, subsequently opting for a change in leadership to ensure what he defined as a successful project outcome. The term “passively” is written between quotes in the original text.

The PI rejects the postdoc concerns about the scientific rigor of the research methodology [the rationale is redacted to ensure the respect of data protection regulations, as it is not necessary for the scope of this report].

In response to the researcher’s observation of 6.4.2022, the PI acknowledged the deviation of the pilot results from the proposed model but maintained that this discrepancy did not invalidate the chosen methodology.

The PI confirms that he found most of the comments of the postdoc researcher during the project activities not helpful. He mentions the researcher’s observations on pitch-noise relation as an example, stating they played no role in the proposal apart from a small excerpt on noise and entropy in Section 2.1.

About the solution proposed by the postdoc researcher, the PI responds that for what regards the future, he needs all forces available to process the experimental data. The PI mentions that he intends to hire a student assistant to contribute to the project tasks, and he would agree with the proposed solution after such assistant has been identified, but he asks the researcher to generally dedicate more time to work in his project. He suggests that if the researcher is dissatisfied with these conditions, the researcher should consider resigning from the project earlier than November rather than expanding the remote-working situation until November.

[8] Counter-Proposal: Shared Workload and Transition to Independent Research

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 24.4.2022

In this e-mail, the postdoc researcher proposes a structured workload to resolve the ongoing leadership and methodological disputes. The researcher proposes to dedicate two days per week to the PI's project and two days per week to his own research (entropy and noise) until November, maintaining the current 32-hour weekly workload.

The proposal further suggests that, starting in November, the postdoc researcher's employment be reduced to two days per week, dedicated exclusively to his own research. This arrangement would allow the PI to utilize the remaining budget to hire a new researcher to fulfill the specific project duties as determined by the PI. The researcher notes that merely resigning in November would offer him no advantage and would result in a personal and professional loss.

[9] PI's Requirement for Full Dedication to Project Tasks

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 25.4.2022

The PI states that if the postdoc researcher intends to remain employed beyond November, he should relocate to Graz immediately. The PI states that a partial cancellation of workload to two days per week without involvement in the project would be logically inconsistent with the project's requirements, reiterating his expectation that the full working capacity of all employees be dedicated to completing the experiment.

The PI further specifies that if the postdoc researcher wishes to maintain his 80% employment status on the project, he must complete a listed series of expected tasks. Notably, this list does not include the possibility for the postdoc researcher to conduct his independent research on entropy and noise.

The PI concludes by reiterating that as a large-scale experiment was commencing, he required the full workforce to be focused on the project to ensure its completion.

[10] Further Statements on Research Freedom and Proposal Authorship

Type: E-mail

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 26.4.2022

The PI states that if the postdoc researcher wants to keep working until the end of the project in full employment, the PI expects the postdoc researcher to dedicate at least half the time to the experiment.

The PI states that he changed the authors' order in the project proposal, placing his name as author and the postdoc researcher's name as co-author.

[11] First Contact with the University Ombudsman and Decision

Type: E-mail

From: University Ombudsman (University of Music and Performing Arts Graz)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 2.5.2022

Over the following several days, the postdoc researcher and PI engaged in a heated correspondence with the Representative for the Safeguarding of Good Scientific Practice of the University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG) in copy.

The postdoc researcher reported feeling prevented from conducting his own research. The PI responded that he was now conceding the postdoc researcher full freedom to dedicate his entire workload to his own research.

The University Ombudsman reviewed the case based on this correspondence that occurred after the postdoc researcher involved him, without requesting a formal allegation with corresponding evidence from the postdoc researcher.

In the decision released on 2.5.2022, the University Ombudsman reports that no clear evidence of scientific misconduct was observed, since the PI was now offering a significant amount of freedom to the postdoc researcher. The University Ombudsman states that the way in which the PI uses his authority could be a matter for upcoming talks. The decision does not include an investigation on how this authority was used in the past. The University Ombudsman suggests setting up a mediation process.

The University Ombudsman concludes that he has found no clear evidence of scientific misconduct, as “most issues should have been agreed on before submitting the project.” However, the University Ombudsman did not verify whether a previous understanding was actually in place. The letter of the PI confirming that an agreement in project leadership informed the change in project destination (Stand-alone project) [7] was never formally reviewed because a formal allegation was not submitted.

[12] Inquiry Regarding Procedural Requirements and FWF Appeal Option

Type: E-mail

From: University Ombudsman (University of Music and Performing Arts Graz)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 2.5.2022

After receiving the Ombudsman's decision, the postdoc researcher sent an email to the University Ombudsman asking him whether he did not need to view any allegation before stating a decision. The postdoc researcher reports that he was preparing such an allegation.

In his response from 2.5.2022, the University Ombudsman states that it is not necessary to send him additional information at the current moment, and that the postdoc researcher could appeal to the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for a more thorough examination of the case.

[13] Submission of Allegations of Research Misconduct to the Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

Type: PDF

From: Postdoc Researcher

To: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

Date: 16.5.2022

The postdoc researcher submits a 10-page formal allegation to the representative of the FWF tasked with processing allegations of misconduct involving researchers affiliated with projects funded by the agency. The main allegation focuses on the claim that the PI unjustly dismissed the research approach of the postdoc researcher despite:

- 1) The presence of an agreement on project leadership informing the condition for the change in PI, which was abrogated as soon as the project activities started.
- 2) The fact that the PI made this change in direction and leadership based on the claim that the researcher's approach was fundamentally flawed, while the postdoc researcher provided concrete evidence that his original approach was actually promising.
- 3) The fact that no dissatisfaction with the postdoc researcher's performance was expressed before the sudden change in project leadership, and that the core hypothesis on entropy informing the approved grant proposal was abandoned with this change in PI.

The researcher includes evidence of a discussion regarding project leadership that occurred prior to submission, which informed the transition from a Lise Meitner program to a Stand-alone project. Specifically, it includes his own letter [6] showing that the change in PI was conceded based on the suggestion that the postdoc researcher would lead the project, and the response of the PI [7] stating that the postdoc researcher was right and the PI initially hoped for the postdoc researcher to lead the project but soon realized that the project could not be accomplished that way. The researcher also includes the PI's statement in which his research approach based on entropy was considered inadequate [4]. The researcher also includes direct preliminary research data confirming the validity of his original approach.

The claim of the postdoc researcher is that this unjust dismissal of the approved research hypothesis and his immediate exclusion from project leadership—despite a previous understanding on the topic—constitutes an obstruction of his right to conduct his planned research. This is argued on the grounds that the project proposal was originally conceived and developed for the promotion of young scientists and that this scope never changed (e.g., the intended writing of a monograph to serve as a habilitation), even after the change in PI and funding scheme.

The postdoc researcher includes evidence highlighting a potential attempt to deny the researcher the time to conduct his research, particularly attaching the letter [9] in which the PI refused the possibility of reducing the employment of the postdoc researcher to two days per week to conduct his own research, stating that he required the full workforce for his own project. This suggests that the researcher may not have been provided with the research freedom that informed the project's original purpose.

[14] FWF Procedural Request to Redact Personal Correspondence

Type: E-mail

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 16.5.2022

The representative of the FWF informs the postdoc researcher that, due to data protection regulations, no personal communication—such as emails or instant messaging—can be considered without the consent of the third parties involved. The representative informs the postdoc researcher that, without this consent, these communications will be deleted.

The representative therefore asks the postdoc researcher to remove any direct quotations from his complaint letter.

[15] Decision of the FWF on the Submitted Allegations

Type: DOCX

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 5.7.2022

The decision of the FWF, dated 5.7.2022 states that no scientific misconduct was identified, as the authors' contributions were clearly reported in the application. It further notes that, according to the funding agreement, the PI is authorized to instruct the project staff.

The FWF states, however, that they encourage the project leader and staff to work out a concrete plan and signed agreement to allow the staff member to implement his ideas within the framework of the project. The FWF suggests that, if this option is not viable, another option for the postdoc researcher is to implement his ideas as an applicant of the ESPRIT program.

Finally, the FWF recommends calling on the support of the institution for the mediation process.

The statement of the FWF does not directly inform on the topic of obstruction of research (misconduct type 2.5 of the GWP guidelines of the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity).

[16] FWF Clarification on Research Time and Referral to the ÖAWI

Type: E-mail

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 8.8.2022

Following the FWF's initial decision, the PI offered a new work agreement to the postdoc researcher. The postdoc researcher contacted the FWF to report that, in his view, the PI's proposed solution did not provide adequate protection against potential retaliation.

In their response on 8.8.2022, the FWF asked why the researcher could not design a new proposal for the ESPRIT program during the remaining term of his employment. In doing so, the FWF suggested that the postdoc researcher is permitted to use his working time to develop a new research proposal.

The FWF also informed the postdoc researcher that if he wishes to challenge the FWF's decision regarding scientific misconduct, he may contact the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI).

[17] Submission of Allegations of Research Misconduct to the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

Type: PDF

From: Postdoc Researcher

To: Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

Date: 7.9.2022

Following the FWF's recommendation to appeal to the ÖAWI and a preliminary meeting with ÖAWI staff on 23.8.2022, the postdoc researcher submitted a formal allegation through the agency's whistleblowing web portal.

Unlike the FWF, the ÖAWI did not require the redaction of direct quotations from personal correspondence within the main text of the submission.

In the submission, the postdoc researcher emphasizes that the understanding regarding project leadership was abrogated prematurely and that his hypothesis on entropy—the theoretical foundation of the research approach in the approved proposal—was dismissed without adequate justification.

The researcher states that he was neither permitted to develop the project nor provided with the time to conduct independent research activities in a constructive environment. He characterizes this as an obstruction of the agreed-upon scope of research.

The researcher reports that this obstruction continued even after the FWF's decision; the PI attempted to direct him toward a series of arbitrarily chosen tasks until the end of the project term. This occurred despite the FWF's specific recommendation that the PI and researcher collaboratively develop a work plan to implement the researcher's ideas.

These tasks were documented in an attached email dated 5.8.2022, in which the PI instructed the postdoc researcher to produce short written analyses of several musical works included in the project, specifically excluding the 23 works for which experimental data was already being collected.

[18] First Decision of the Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

Type: PDF

From: Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 26.4.2023

The ÖAWI admits the submission for scrutiny deeming it well-documented. The Commission chooses to not investigate allegations concerning the timeframe prior to the submission of allegations to the FWF by the postdoc researcher, treating the FWF's administrative decision as a final ruling on research integrity for that period.

The ÖAWI investigates misconduct types 2.5 and 2.8 (§3 para. 2 no. 5 and no. 8 of the GWP Guidelines) only for the facts happening after the FWF's decision, finding no misconduct. The Commission characterizes certain allegations as "partially misleading and inaccurate." The allegations that are considered partially misleading and inaccurate are not mentioned.

[19] Exclusion of the Postdoc Researcher from the Project and Change of Location

Type: Various

From: PI

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: After 5.7.2022

Following the submission of research integrity allegations to the FWF, the PI formally concluded the researcher's involvement in the project. The PI justified this exclusion by citing in an e-mail from 9.5.2022 a breakdown in professional trust and stating that the researcher's methodological critiques rendered further collaboration "not beneficial."

Consequently, the PI implemented the following measures:

- The researcher was moved to a separate office.
- The PI declined the use of project funds for conference fees (NoiseFloor 2024) after the researcher's termination of employment, despite the contribution being submitted during the project.
- While the PI requested a project budget extension through April 2024 to support team members to work on the project, this support was not extended to the postdoc researcher.
- Selectively removed the profile picture of the postdoc researcher from the project website after the termination of his contract.

[20] KUG Preliminary Examination Regarding the Selective Removal of Researcher Profile Data

Type: PDF

From: Vice-Rector for Research and Quality Management (KUG)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 10.7.2024

Following the selective removal of the researcher's profile picture from the project website, while other former team members' photos remained, the researcher notified the University of a potential retaliatory act since it was affecting only a member previously contacting the Ombudsman. The researcher suggests that this selective removal of data effectively constitutes a symbolic erasure of his contribution and an attempt to lower his visibility.

The PI confirmed the removal in correspondence dated 10.6.2024, citing an intended website update that remained unfinished for several months.

Following a preliminary examination, the University concluded the removal was an "oversight." The decision letter provided no documentary evidence to support the claim of an accidental omission.

[21] **ÖAWI Rejection of Investigation into the Selective Removal of Researcher Data**

Type: PDF

From: Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 9.12.2024

Following the preliminary decision by the KUG Vice-Rector, the researcher was directed to contact the ÖAWI for a secondary investigation into the selective removal of his profile data.

The ÖAWI declined to open a formal investigation. The Agency stated that the selective removal of a researcher’s profile picture—conducted without the researcher’s consent after they had submitted allegations of misconduct—did not constitute academic misconduct under the GWP Guidelines Type 2.8 (§3 para. 2 no. 8). This specific guideline pertains to “creating disadvantages to the career advancement of junior scientists and researchers who have reported potential research misconduct (whistleblowers).”

The Agency reasoned that since the researcher’s biography remained on the site, the removal of the image could be interpreted by a hypothetical visitor as a measure related to data protection requested by the candidate rather than a retaliatory act. In this sense, the absence of a profile picture did not significantly impair the researcher’s reputation or career advancement, thereby failing to meet the threshold for documented “disadvantage” required for initiating an investigation.

[22] ÖAWI Assessment on Authorship and Special Permission Around Confidentiality to Allow the PI to Submit it to a Journal

Type: PDF

From: Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 11.10.2024

On 19.8.2024, the PI and the research team submitted a request to the ÖAWI for a ruling on authorship for scientific articles emerging from the project. This request, including a specific quote from the resulting ruling, is publicly available via a statement by the team on the project website.

On 11.10.2024, the ÖAWI issues a decision on the merits of authorship, stating that the postdoc researcher did not meet the required criteria. However, before releasing this decision, the ÖAWI did not provide the postdoc researcher with the opportunity to respond to the team's allegations, nor the possibility to demonstrate that an eventual exclusion from the project may have prevented him from meeting the remaining criteria (e.g., final approval of the manuscript).²

The ÖAWI grants the PI a special permission to waive standard confidentiality protocols, allowing him to communicate the outcome and the ruling to the editor of a scientific journal. This waiver has been utilized by the PI in September 2025 to submit the ruling to a journal editor after the postdoc researcher had raised formal concerns regarding scientific methodology and authorship in a published article emerging from the project.

² The researcher notes that the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) guidelines, "Defining the Role of Authors and Contributors," specify that authorship criteria should not be used as a means to disqualify colleagues who otherwise meet the criteria by denying them the opportunity to fulfill the remaining requirements.

[23] Public Statement by the PI and Research Team Regarding Allegations of Misconduct

Type: Online Text
From: Research Team
To: Public
Date: 19.9.2025

The research team publishes a statement stating that the PI gave “the PDR the opportunity to implement his own ideas within the scope of his project work, provided he also participated (to a correspondingly limited extent) in the ongoing research of the rest of the team (PI and DR1). Throughout the entire project duration, the PDR was able to develop his ideas completely freely, without any interference from the PI or the rest of the project team. [...] After the PDR first filed a complaint on April 27, 2022, regarding alleged violations of the GWP by the PI, further continuous collaboration was no longer possible due to a breakdown in trust. From April 2022 onward, the PDR continued its independent research and thus made no further significant contribution to the PoD project.”

The research team then label the actions of the postdoc researcher as illegitimate whistleblowing and a tentative obstruction of the research activities of the research team, since authorities on research integrity found no misconduct in multiple reviews.

[24] **ÖAWI Final Decision and Assertion of Discretionary Power Regarding the Research Team’s Public Statement**

Type: Whistleblowing Submission

From: Austrian Agency for Scientific Integrity (ÖAWI)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 14.1.2026

On 18.10.2025, the researcher requested that the ÖAWI address the “clear state of affairs” claimed by the research team in their public statement, noting that unfair attempts to diminish a scientist’s reputation (e.g. “illegitimate whistleblowing”) constitute scientific misconduct.

The submission argued that the PI’s public claim—that the researcher was given the opportunity to implement independent ideas—was factually contradicted by internal correspondence. The postdoc researcher claimed that, in said correspondence, the PI had explicitly rejected a request for part-time independent research, citing the need for the whole workforce for his project. The researcher further noted that the team characterized a preliminary authorship judgment from the ÖAWI as a “clear state of affairs,” despite the researcher being denied the opportunity to provide a response during that judgment's formation.

In the letter dated 14.1.2026, the ÖAWI declines to open an investigation. The Agency states that its guidelines preclude the resubmission of allegations that have already been addressed.³ Because the new submission included context from previous allegations, the Agency determines the request for a new investigation could not be accepted and invited the researcher to submit new allegations in accordance with the mentioned requirements.

The letter concludes by asserting the Agency's discretionary power in accepting and processing submissions from individuals, effectively finalizing the institutional review of the matter.

³ In a previous communication (23.09.2024), the ÖAWI stated that cases cannot be reopened unless substantial new evidence is provided.

[25] Public Exchange Regarding Whistleblowing and Formal Recourse

Type: Facebook Post

From: Research Team Member

To: Public

Date: 13.7.2025

Following the release of a campaign video regarding his experience of the case on Facebook on 13.7.2025, a project team member posts a public rebuttal. He labels the postdoc researcher's allegations as "false accusations," as he is familiar with the project and its structures. He further argues that social media is an inappropriate platform for such discussions and invites readers to contact him directly for a "clearer picture" of events.

The postdoc researcher replies by identifying the team member's conflict of interest and noting that whistleblowing often necessitates public platforms when internal channels fail, citing historical precedents like Theranos. He explicitly invites the team member to utilize the legal system or file a formal complaint with the ÖAWI if he believes the facts presented were manipulated or inappropriate.

[26] Opening of an Investigation by a Scientific Journal

Type: E-mail

From: Journal Editor

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 5.12.2025

Following the submission of a 50-page analysis by the researcher highlighting concerns regarding the reliability of a published article, the journal's editorial board formally opens an investigation into the scientific reliability and methodology of the work.

[27] Exclusion of the Postdoc Researcher from the ESPRIT Program

Type: E-mail

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 8.1.2025

In its decision of 5.7.2022 [15], the FWF Executive Board proposed two options to resolve the dispute regarding the researcher's independent ideas. The first recommended option (3a) was for the PI and researcher to develop a work plan and timetable to allow the postdoc researcher to implement his ideas within the existing project framework. The second recommended option (3b) stated that if no agreement could be reached, an alternative option for the staff member for realizing his research ideas was to assume the role of an applicant within the FWF's ESPRIT program.

Following the failure to achieve a signed agreement under the first option, the researcher proceeded with the ESPRIT application. However, the resubmission was rejected on 8.1.2025 because the researcher no longer fulfilled the 5-year post-PhD window requirement. This resulted in the procedural closure of the alternative path explicitly suggested by the FWF as a resolution to the conflict.

The FWF subsequently suggested the postdoc researcher submit his proposal to the Principal Investigator Project program. The researcher noted that the two programs are not equivalent in objectives or requirements; a proposal specifically tailored to the career-development goals of ESPRIT is not inherently adequate for a PI Project. This discrepancy was corroborated by an anonymous peer-review which rated the project proposal as "outstanding" specifically for meeting the exact objectives of the ESPRIT program, rather than those of a standard PI Project.

[28] Request of Clarification About the Processing of Personal Correspondence in Evaluation of Scientific Misconduct

Type: E-mail

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 20.11.2025 and 27.1.2026

In two instances (20.11.2025 and 16.1.2026), the researcher asked the FWF for clarification regarding the processing of personal correspondence within whistleblowing procedures. Specifically, the researcher asked whether such correspondence would be considered as evidence in future submissions. On 20.11.2025, the FWF discontinued communication without clarifying the specific inquiry.

On 16.1.2026, the researcher repeated the inquiry and requested the legal references motivating the exclusion of personal correspondence from his 2022 whistleblowing case [13]. The FWF responded on 27.1.2026, stating the case followed ÖAWI procedures, but did not provide the specific legal terms that precluded the consideration of the correspondence.

The researcher replied on 27.1.2026, noting a possible inconsistency: while both the ÖAWI and FWF purportedly follow the same procedures, the ÖAWI accepted quotations from personal correspondence without requiring redactions, unlike the FWF.

[29] Refusal to Support Costs for Research Presentation Post-Employment

Type: E-mail

From: Austrian Science Fund (FWF)

To: Postdoc Researcher

Date: 31.1.2024—21.3.2024

The researcher requested reimbursement for costs to present a peer-reviewed paper at a conference; while the paper was submitted during his contract, the event took place post-employment.

The PI, the University, and the FWF declined any support. The PI redirected the request to other personnel without addressing the merit. The University cited the end of employment as an absolute barrier to reimbursement. The FWF confirmed that while the PI holds sole financial responsibility over the budget, the FWF still requires full funding acknowledgement in the presentation.